

FORENSIC ACCOUNTING STRATEGIES AND CORPORATE FRAUD DETECTION: THE MODERATING INFLUENCE OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection in Nigeria. This study employed the explanatory research design, relying on survey strategy. From the target population of 2,540 active licensed members-in-practice of the firms of the two reputable professional accounting organizations that offer forensic accounting services in Nigeria, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) and Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN), a sample size of 346 was chosen at random. Data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire. The data collected were analysed through Ordinary Least Squares in Multiple Regression Analysis using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 22 and E-view version 12. The study revealed that Fraud detection mechanisms and fraud litigation support services were statistically significant; while, fraud investigation techniques were statistically insignificant. The study also found that, when taken as a whole, emerging technologies significantly moderate corporate fraud detection and forensic accounting strategies. However, on the individual forensic accounting strategies, while the interaction between fraud investigation techniques and emerging technologies showed significant moderating influence on corporate fraud detection; fraud detection mechanisms and fraud litigation support services did not show evidence of moderating influence on forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection. In line with the findings, the study recommended the need for forensic accounting practitioners to always engage in proactive measures in the areas of forensic accounting and emerging technology that will inhibit the menace of fraud and fraud related misconducts in Nigerian business environment.

Keywords: forensic accounting strategies, emerging technologies, corporate fraud detection, professional accounting bodies, forensic accounting services providers

INTRODUCTION

Fraud in any form, including corporate fraud has become a major challenge in the modern business environment. The efforts to manage this challenge has been on the business discourse globally to reduce the adverse consequences it has on individuals, organisations in both private and public sectors of any economy, and the society as a whole, when it occurs (Alfordy, 2022; Wells, 2011; Zimelman et al. 2012). Fraud is an intentional deception that seeks unlawful benefits and it encompasses all forms of financial malpractices (Okoh, 2021). The presence of fraud increases the operational costs of the organizations. This was reflected by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE, 2024) global fraud survey reports and Financial Institutions Training Centers (FITC, 2024) annual fraud and forgeries survey reports in Nigeria

The occurrences of corporate frauds have great devastating consequences on a lot of stakeholders; such as inability of investors and creditors alike to recoup their huge investments, among others (Awolowo, 2019). These brought concern to the effective corporate governance to guarantee corporate survival and sustainability.

Awolowo (2019) noticed that the reliance on age long method of auditing is perceived to be responsible for the series of audit failures, corporate collapses and financial statement fraud being witnessed overtime. This situation is also compounded by the accounting firms using traditional auditing techniques of rule-based system for fraud prevention and detection that are nor sustainable over the years (Lawal et al., 2023; Okoh & Uwaifo, 2021). Scholars have alluded that modern business environment have become complex and diverse for business operations apparently due to globalisation and advancement in emerging technologies, which provides opportunity for financial malfeasance and business failures (Alfordy, 2022). Therefore, adoption of forensic accounting strategies and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, blockchain to combat fraud is in response to the worrisome increase in corporate financial fraud (Gupta, 2022).

Awolowo (2019) argued that forensic accounting as a tool for fighting frauds, in combination with emerging technologies is a perfect mix and has also been advocated as very effective and efficient in fraud prevention and detection, which may compliment the age long traditional auditing techniques and procedures that are acclaimed to be insufficient to curtail financial frauds, coupled with the fraudulent activities of fraudsters who are continuously in search of and use of same advanced technologies to sustain their fraudulent behaviours. Literature have it that forensic accounting is an innovation in the field of accounting, and its interaction with emerging technologies suitable in the domain of fraud management, would effective in fraud detection in the corporate business world for growth and sustainability (Hossain, 2023; Lawal et al., 2020). However, there is paucity of such empirical evidence in Nigeria. Hence, this study aims to fill this gap by replicating the same in Nigeria. The objective of this study is to examine the moderating influence of emerging technologies (artificial intelligence, machine learning, blockchain) on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies (fraud detection mechanisms, fraud investigation techniques, fraud litigation support services) and corporate fraud detection in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Corporate fraud detection could be described as the process of identifying and discovery fraud acts that were concealed and the perpetrator from being uncover in order to prevent economic and financial resources from being stolen or obtain illegally (Oyerogba, 2021).

Forensic accounting is the application of accounting knowledge, principles, methods, inter-personal skills, analytical skills to look beyond the numbers to detect the various frauds and other fraudulent acts embedded in accounting records (Gupta, 2022). Forensic accounting strategies in this study, therefore, comprise a plan of action to detect or identify fraud and fraudulent acts in corporate organisations so as to reduce the threat of fraud to corporations for the benefit of all parties involved (Halvorson, 2024).

Emerging technology is all encompassing as they have been used or applied virtually in every sector of any economy including financial fraud domain. Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, big data analytics, and blockchain, are generally perceived to effective and efficient in fraud prevention, detection, and investigation operations (Mohanty et al., 2023).

Empirical Review

Fraud Detection Mechanisms and Corporate Fraud Detection

Aziz and Othman (2021) investigated if fraud awareness, fraud prevention and detection strategies and anti-fraud technology have significant relationship with the public auditors' perceptions of the efficacy of fraud prevention and detection in the public sector. Guided by fraud triangle theory, the research revealed that fraud awareness, as well as fraud prevention and detection strategies have positive relations to perceived efficacy of fraud prevention and detection.

Ewa (2022) evaluated forensic accounting techniques on fraud management in the public sector ministries, departments, and agencies in Nigeria. The study examined the use of trend analysis, data mining, and accounting ratios techniques in detection and prevention of fraudulent activities within the ministries, departments, and agencies. The study found that using forensic accounting techniques including trend analysis, accounting ratios; and data mining might greatly improve fraud detection. In a study conducted by Rashid et al. (2022), it was found that internal control system was the most effective method of preventing and detecting corporate fraud as a component of good governance. Hence we therefore hypothesize thus:

H₀₁. Fraud prevention and detection mechanisms (good internal control; fraud awareness training; positive work environment; tips from whistleblowers; segregation of duties) do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

Fraud Investigation Techniques and Corporate Fraud Detection

Okoye et al. (2020) examined the effect of forensic investigation techniques in detecting occupational fraud in the public sector. The study utilised a cross-sectional survey methodology and purposeful sampling technique. The study found that forensic investigation techniques and fraud detection in the public sector have substantial positive association.

Alhassan (2021) empirically evaluated the relationship between forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the Nigerian ministries. The primary source of data for the study was a questionnaire utilised in a survey design. The study found among others that forensic accounting

is useful to help Nigerian ministries investigate and find fraud; as well as beneficial in fraud prevention and detection. We therefore, hypothesize that:

H₀₂. Fraud investigation techniques (predication; conducting honesty test; document examination; surveillance and covert operation; interview and interrogation) do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

Fraud Litigation Support Services and Corporate fraud Detection

Micah et al. (2023) examined the use of litigation support and forensic accounting in revealing intricate financial transactions and strategies that are employed in Nigerian money laundering instances. The research design employed in the study was qualitative, and the data was analysed through content analysis, secondary sources, and agency theory guidance. The research indicates that the examined cases highlight the significance of forensic accounting and litigation support in revealing intricate financial transactions and strategies that are employed in Nigerian money laundering instances. A study conducted by Oko (2023) that examined the effect of forensic accounting services on fraud rate management by listed banks in Nigeria, discovered that the management of fraud rates in Nigeria's listed banks was greatly improved by expert advice, fraud investigation, and litigation support services.

Chepngeno and Fred (2020) worried by the alarming increase in corporate fraud around the world and relieved by the importance of forensic accounting, examined to establish the effects of litigation support services on fraud mitigation in firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Primary data was collected from purposefully selected staff members working with the listed firms. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to the collected data using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 and Statistics and data (STATA) version 13 analytical tools. The study found significant relationship between litigation support services and fraud mitigation.

Sulaiman et al. (2023) examined the significant difference between forensic accounting and fraud identification in the Nigerian public sector. A survey-based research design was employed, and to test the hypotheses, analysis of variance was employed. The results showed a strong correlation between forensic accounting and litigation support services in Nigerian courts, as well as effectiveness in identifying and preventing fraud in the public sector of Nigeria.

The hypothesis, therefore states that:

H₀₃. Fraud Litigation support services (alternative dispute resolution; expert consultant; expert witness; alternative dispute resolution mediator or arbitrator; dispute participant) do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

Emerging Technologies Moderating Influence on Forensic Accounting Strategies and Corporate Fraud Detection

Ali et al. (2024) examined how artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain (BC), and data analytics (DA) can improve forensic accounting techniques to enhance the efficiency of fraud detection. The study found that businesses with large number of transactions and have applied blockchain technology showed better transparency and traceability, leading to improved detection of fraud. The study comes to the conclusion that forensic accounting efficiency in fraud detection and prevention is greatly improved by the use of frontier technology like blockchain, artificial intelligence, and data analytics.

Mohanty et al. (2023) examined the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in financial fraud detection analyse and evaluate various artificial intelligence based solutions and its impact on the betterment of the business landscape. The study found, among others, that artificial intelligence has been a game changer and has received wider ramifications than just reducing the instances of financial frauds.

Navaneethakrishnan et al. (2023) reviewed research paper with a view to explore the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in the field of fraud detection and prevention, used systematic literature review approach. The findings showed the effectiveness of AI and ML techniques in fraud detection and prevention. The study also revealed that these technologies have the ability to detect previously unknown fraud patterns, familiar to evolving fraudulent attitudes, and reduce false positives, and enhances the overall accuracy and efficiency of fraud detection systems.

Malladhi (2023) reviewed the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning for fraud detection in forensic accounting. The study, among other findings, revealed that artificial intelligence and machine learning enhance forensic accounting through automated analysis of massive datasets and identification of complex fraudulent patterns. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H₀₄. Emerging technologies (artificial intelligence, machine learning, blockchain) have no significant moderating influence on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection.

Theoretical Framework

This study anchored on the agency theory, and fraud triangle theory that would help to have more understanding on the moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection. The agency theory developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976) was used as the mirror to help understand the relationship between the owners of corporations and the board of directors, management, and other employees of the corporate organisation entrusted with the power to direct and control the affairs of the corporation, resulting often times agency problem, conflict of interest on the part of management. Through agency theory, the role of audit came to light that they are to bridge the conflict of interest and add credibility to the financial reports for users' informed decision making.

The fraud triangle theory developed by Cressey (1953) was used to explain why agents (management and other employees) violate trust position and commit fraud. Cressey (1953) posits that for fraud to occur, three factors must be present, pressure/incentive, opportunity, rationalization/attitude to justify action; understanding of these elements would help the organisation to provide anti-fraud programmes to curtail it. However, where fraud occurred, fraud investigators will be guided on how to follow predication to deal with the problems. Therefore, is expected that the understanding of the dynamics of these theories would have significant positive effect in forensic accounting interaction with emerging technologies on corporate fraud detection, prevention, mitigation and resolution.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed explanatory research design, relying on the survey strategy. Data for the study were through primary source, using structured questionnaire administered through Google Form in order to reach wider respondents of the target population - the trained forensic accounting professionals, providing forensic accounting services in Nigeria. This was used because it allows the collection of data from a large number of respondents; it is relatively easy to explain and to understand in comparing the relationship between variables (Saunders et al., 2019).

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) and the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN), two legally recognised professional accounting organisations that offer forensic accounting services in Nigeria, comprise the study's population. However, as of October 31, 2024, the target population consisted of the 2,540 active licensed members-in-practice of the firms of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria of the corresponding professional accounting bodies in Nigeria, comprising 2,133 ICAN active licensed members-in-practice and 407 ANAN active licensed members-in-practice, respectively.

Distribution of the target population

	Number	Percentage
Number of target population (ICAN and ANAN)	2,540	100
Number of ICAN active licenced member-in-practice	2,133	83.98
Number of ANAN active licenced member-in-practice	407	16.02

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique, Yamane (1967) formula: $n = N / [1 + N(e)^2]$; where: n = sample size; N = population of the study; e = error limit (5% or 0.05 on the basis of 95% confidence level) was used to determine the study sample size. The sample size for the study was 346 active licensed members-in-practice of ICAN and ANAN Firms of Chartered Accountants that provides forensic accounting services in Nigeria. Sample size from ICAN stands 291, and sample size from ANAN stands 55; as showed thus:

Distribution of the sample size from target population

	Number	Percentage
Sample size from the target population (ICAN and ANAN)	346	100
Number of ICAN active licenced member-in-practice	291	84.10
Number of ANAN active licenced member-in-practice	55	15.90

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Model Specification

This study adapted the work of Lawal et al. (2020) on whose study's model this study expanded by introducing additional explanatory variables (fraud detection mechanisms, forensic accounting expertise, and forensic accounting practice) with the perception that larger explanatory or predictor variables have more predictive ability on a phenomena or the predicted; and also a moderating influence. Their model equation is indicated thus:

Lawal et al. (2020):

$Y = f(X)$, where: Y = Dependent variable (Fraud Detection); X = Independent variable (Forensic Accounting) X = X₁, X₂, X₃; X = Forensic Accounting (FA); X₁ = Forensic Litigation (FL); X₂ = Forensic Investigation (FI); X₃ = Forensic Accounting Investigative Skills (FAIS)

Functional Relationship: $FD = f(FL, FI, FAIS)$;

$$FD = \beta_0 + \beta_1FL + \beta_2FI + \beta_3FAIS + \text{eit} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Then,

This study model equation is indicted thus:

$$Y = f(X) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$Y = f(X)*M \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where: X = Forensic accounting strategies (independent variables); M = Emerging technologies (moderating variables); Y = Corporate fraud detection (dependent variable)

Where:

X = X₁, X₂, X₃, (fraud detection mechanisms, fraud investigation techniques, fraud litigation support services).

Corporate fraud detection = $f(\text{Forensic accounting strategies})$

$$CFDET = f(FDMC, FITQ, FLSS) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Model 1: Forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection

Model stated in the functional form as follows:

$$CFDET = f(FDMC, FITQ, FLSS) \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Expressing equation (5) in econometric form, the model is stated as:

$$CFDET = \beta_0 + \beta_1FDMC + \beta_2FITQ + \beta_3FLSS + \mu \dots \dots (6)$$

Where: CFDET = Corporate fraud detection; FDMC = Fraud detection mechanisms; FITQ = Fraud investigation techniques; FLSS = Fraud Litigation support services

Introducing moderating variable into equation (6)

Model 2: Moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection

Corporate fraud = $f(\text{Forensic accounting strategies})*(\text{Emerging technologies})$

$$CFDET = f(FDMC, FITQ, FLSS,)*(ETEC) \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Expressing equation (7) in econometric form, the model is stated as:

$$CFDET = \beta_0 + \beta_1FDMC + \beta_2FITQ + \beta_3FLSS + \beta_4ETEC + (\beta_5FAS*ETEC) + \mu \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Where: CFDET = Corporate fraud detection (dependent variable)

Forensic Accounting Strategies: FDMC = Fraud detection mechanisms; FITQ = Fraud investigation techniques; FLSS = Fraud litigation support services; FAS = Forensic Accounting Strategies (independent variable); ETEC = Emerging technologies (moderating variable).

μ = Error term; β_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = Coefficient of the independent variables

A-priori expectations: β_1 to $\beta_5 > 0$

Operationalisation of Variables

The elements for operationalisation and measurement of variables have been segmented along the identified dimensions of dependent, independent, moderating, control variables of this study. The variables were measured using a Likert-type five-point scale. The details are shown in Table

Operationalisation and measurement of research variables

S/No	Variables	Type	Measurement	Source
1	Corporate fraud detection	Dependent	Likert-type five point scale Qs 1-5	Lawal et al. (2020);
2	Fraud detection mechanisms	Independent	Likert-type five point scale Qs 6-10	Aziz and Othman (2021);
3	Fraud investigation techniques	Independent	Likert-type five point scale Qs 11-15	Lawal et al. (2020);
4	Fraud litigation support services	Independent	Likert-type five point scale Qs 16-20	Lawal et al. (2020); Oko (2023)
5	Emerging technologies	Moderating	Likert-type five point scale Qs 21-25	Mohanty et al. (2023)

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2025)

Research Instrument

The survey strategy was adopted using a questionnaire designed to elicit responses on the moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection. The questionnaire was segmented into four sections A to D thus: questions in relation to corporate fraud detection; forensic accounting strategies consist of (fraud detection mechanisms, fraud investigation techniques, fraud litigation support services); emerging technologies (artificial intelligence, machine learning, blockchain) respectively. A five-point Likert-type scale—strongly agree (5 points), agree (4 points), neutral (3 points), disagree (2 points), and strongly disagree (1 point)—was used to assess the statements on the questionnaire. Responses were based on the individual perception of the issues related to the study. The copies of questionnaire were administered using Google form approach.

Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

The research instrument was standardised through validity and reliability tests. Validity in relation to questionnaire was evaluated by five forensic accounting experts who gave their opinions on the contents of the questionnaire. The ambiguity observed was corrected for the final copy of the

questionnaire. While in relation to the instrument reliability, a pilot study was conducted on 50 respondents who are knowledgeable in the subject matter but are independent of the final respondents of the study to establish reliability and consistency. Cronbach's Alpha approach was used to establish reliability. The details of the test results are showed that the individual values of the variables of Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are, CFDET (0.751), FDMC (0.819), FITQ (0.832), FLSS (0.840), and ETEC (0.837); and the composite value of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.820. Both the individual and the composite Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are indicative of very high reliability as they are greater or stronger than the Saunders et al. (2019) benchmark of 0.70.

Method of Data Analysis

To achieve research objectives of this study, the data that were collected through structured questionnaire were analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistical analyses. Ultimately, the hypotheses of the study were estimated using Multiple Linear Regression analysis. The overall or inferential statistical analyses were done using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 22 and E-View Statistical Analytic Tool version 12. The choice of this method is that it is perceived to have in-depth statistical capacity; and the comprehensiveness and flexibility in quantitative data analysis is a most feature to choose the program above any other alternative (Rahman & Buktadir, 2021).

To avoid spurious results, the study also conducted some regression diagnostic tests such as Normality test, Ramsey RESET test, Multi-collinearity test, Heteroscedasticity test, and Serial Correlation test.

EXTIMATION OF RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data Presentation and Interpretations

Questionnaire Response Rate

The Table is a frequency distribution showing the number and percentage of responses gathered from the distribution of the questionnaire. Out of the 346 copies of questionnaire, 16.18% were incompletely filled and therefore could not be used for the analysis. Consequently, the analysis is based on 83.82% of the original sample size. This figure is still fairly representative of the entire population.

Frequency distribution of filled questionnaire

	N	Percent
Number of filled questionnaire	346	100
Number with incomplete responses	56	16.18
Number with complete responses	290	83.82

Source: Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) Output Extract (2025)

Variable Descriptive Statistics

The characterisation of the variables in this study has been captured using the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. These statistics are based on the average responses for each variable.

Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables

	CFDET	FDMC	FDMC_ET EC	FITQ	FITQ_ET EC	FLSS	FLSS_ETEC	ETEC	
Average	4.18413	8	4.218621	17.93724	0	17.71048	4.173103	17.79324	4.176552
Median	4.20000	0	4.200000	17.60000	0	16.80000	4.200000	17.60000	4.200000
Maximum	5.00000	0	5.000000	25.00000	0	25.00000	5.000000	25.00000	5.000000
Minimum	1.00000	0	1.000000	1.000000	0	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Std. Dev.	0.68591	1	0.667846	4.796686	6	4.951735	0.696581	4.991136	0.679101
Skewness	1.41422	-	1.41422	-	-	1.41422	-	1.41422	-1.199147
Kurtosis	6.45305	3	-1.436345	-0.393304	1.187121	-0.335368	-1.149703	-0.360354	6.096192
Jarque-Bera	240.744	8	307.5463	8.760498	2	5.437301	145.0762	6.278369	185.3368
Probability	0.00000	0	0.000000	0.012522	0	0.065964	0.000000	0.043318	0.000000
Sum	1213.40	0	1223.400	5201.800	0	5136.040	1210.200	5160.040	1211.200
Sum Sq. Dev.	135.967	0	128.8994	6649.368	9	7086.187	140.2302	7199.406	133.2806
Observations	290	290	290	290	290	290	290	290	290

Source: E-Views Version 12 Output Extract (2025)

From the table, corporate fraud detection (CFDET) has a high mean which indicates that respondents strongly agree with the effectiveness of corporate fraud detection strategies. The low standard deviation reflects a consistent agreement among respondents, indicating shared perceptions about the importance of fraud detection measures. Taking a look at the variables incorporating the interaction with emerging technologies (denoted with _ETEC), technology can be seen to enhance the efficacy of forensic accounting strategies.

Generally, the high mean scores across most variables affirm the perceived effectiveness of forensic accounting strategies and emerging technologies in fraud detection.

With respect to the skewness, all variables without interaction have negative skewness values. This indicates that the bulk of the responses are clustered toward the high end of the scale (close to 5), which could mean, most respondents gave relatively high ratings (strongly agree), though a few

lower ratings pull the tail to the left. However, upon interaction, the variables have skewness values that suggest when the variables are interacted, the distributions become more symmetric.

Concerning kurtosis, the values suggests that the distribution is more peaked compared to a normal (mesokurtic) distribution. In the overall, most individual variables show more “peakedness” (leptokurtic) than a perfectly normal distribution.

Histogram Normality Chart

The histogram chart and the values show a left-skewed, leptokurtic distribution of residuals that fails the Jarque-Bera normality test, indicating that the residuals are very unlikely to be normally distributed. However, several studies (Knief & Forstmeier, 2021; Schmidt & Finan, 2018; Tsagris & Pandis, 2021) have reported that violations of normality assumptions in linear regression analysis do not impact bias nor do they impact tests in large sample sizes. That is, linear regression models with residuals deviating from the normal distribution usually still produce valid results. Schmidt and Finan (2018) suggest that instead of focusing on the non-normality which do not connote bias or make result invalid, focus should be on: trends between the residuals and the independent variables; multivariable outlying outcome or predictor values; and general errors in the parametric model, that usually impact results irrespective of sample size.

Correlation of Variables

The extent of association and strength of association between the variables have been captured us due to the categorical nature of the variables.

Correlation of Variables

	CFDET	FDMC	FITQ	FLSS
CFDET	1			
FDMC	0.698001	1		
FITQ	0.662668	0.797582	1	
FLSS	0.691445	0.773140	0.8244666	1

Source: E-Views Version 12 Output Extract (2025)

From the correlation matrix presented in Table, we see that all the explanatory variables, moderator variable exhibit a positive association with corporate fraud detection. This means that improvements in corporate fraud detection are associated with improvements in these variables. Among the explanatory variables, fraud investigation techniques have the weakest association with corporate fraud detection while fraud detection mechanism has the strongest association. These suggest that the latter contributes most to improving corporate fraud detection while the former contributes least. Lastly, the coefficients among the explanatory variables do not provide evidence of multicollinearity as the correlation coefficients are lower than the .90 rule of thumb. The absence of multicollinearity was also supported by multicollinearity test using variance inflation factor (VIF).

Multicollinearity Test

Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 10/16/25 Time: 17:53

Sample: 1 290

Included observations: 290

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
FDMC	0.005181	127.3867	3.104008
FITQ	0.005983	143.4137	3.898771
FLSS	0.005411	130.5372	3.526672
C	0.033095	44.60843	NA

Source: E-Views Version 12 Output Extract (2025)

The decision rule is that if VIF of each explanatory variable is less than 10 (< 10), it will be subjective that it does not correlate with other independent variables. However, if a variable shows a VIF of up to or greater than 10 (≥ 10), then it correlate with other independent variables. Going by the results on the table the values of the VIF are below the benchmark of 10. This suggests that multicollinearity between the variables is not a concern.

Regression Analysis

To test the linear relationship among the variables, the study employed the use of ordinary least squares regression technique. This was used since the variables were averaged thereby transforming the scale from an ordinal measurement to a continuous measurement. To ensure robustness, the expected diagnostic tests were also performed.

Least Squares Model

Dependent Variable: CFDET

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/16/25 Time: 17:39

Sample: 1 290

Included observations: 290

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FDMC	0.373349	0.071979	5.186897	0.0000
FITQ	0.105709	0.077350	1.366622	0.1728
FLSS	0.316966	0.073559	4.309031	0.0000
C	0.846713	0.181920	4.654307	0.0000
R-squared	0.547441	Mean dependent var	4.184138	
Adjusted R-squared	0.542694	S.D. dependent var	0.685911	
S.E. of regression	0.463844	Akaike info criterion	1.315158	
Sum squared resid	61.53315	Schwarz criterion	1.365777	
Log likelihood	-186.6980	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.335439	
F-statistic	115.3205	Durbin-Watson stat	1.889392	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
BG Serial				
Correlation	3.288512			
Prob Chi-Square(2)	0.193200			
BPG Heterosk Test	3.833144			
Prob. Chi-Square	0.280100			
Ramsey RESET	0.228993			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.632600			

Source: E-Views Version 12 Output Extract (2025)

The Table above presents the regression analysis that examined the relationship between the dependent variable (CFDET – Corporate Fraud Detection) and the independent variables (FDMC, FITQ, FLSS). Key indicators, including coefficients, t-statistics, p-values, and overall model fit metrics, provide insights into the significance and explanatory power of the predictors.

The R-squared tells us that 54.7% of the variation in corporate fraud detection is explained by the independent variables in the model, indicating a moderately strong fit. After accounting for the number of predictors, the adjusted R-squared shows that 54.3% of the variation in the dependent variable (CFDET) is still explained, confirming the model's robustness. The p-value and F-statistic of 115.3 show that the model as a whole is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), demonstrating that

the independent variables (forensic accounting strategies) collectively influence CFDET. The Durbin-Watson Statistic is 1.889. This value is close to 2, indicating no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. The insignificant p-value ($p = 0.193$) of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test provides additional evidence for this. The Table also reveals no evidence of heteroskedasticity as the p-value ($p = 0.280$) of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test is greater than 5%. In addition, there is no misspecification detected in the model as evidenced by the insignificant Ramsey RESET Test ($p = 0.636$).

Based on the individual t-statistics of the explanatory variables, it is observed that FDMC has a significant positive ($t = 5.187, p = 0.000$) impact on CFDET. A unit increase in FDMC is associated with a 0.373 unit increase in CFDET, underscoring the importance of robust fraud detention measures. FITQ does not significantly ($t = 1.367, p = 0.173$) contribute to CFDET in this model. This suggests that while fraud investigation techniques are important, its isolated impact on fraud detection might be limited or overshadowed by other factors. FLSS has a significant positive ($t = 4.309, p = 0.000$) impact on CFDET and a unit increase in FLSS is associated with a 0.317 unit increase in CFDET, underscoring the importance of fraud litigation support services.

Least Squares Model (Moderator-EETEC)

Dependent Variable: CFDET

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/17/25 Time: 19:20

Sample: 1 290

Included observations: 290

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FDMC	0.341917	0.452386	0.755809	0.4504
FDMC_ETEC	0.002615	0.113785	0.022978	0.9817
FITQ	-0.796580	0.447474	-1.780171	0.0761
FITQ_ETEC	0.221452	0.111249	1.990592	0.0475
FLSS	0.936137	0.473957	1.975153	0.0492
FLSS_ETEC	-0.180069	0.119244	-1.510081	0.1321
C	1.383429	0.252586	5.477056	0.0000

R-squared	0.566271	Mean dependent var	4.184138
Adjusted R-squared	0.557076	S.D. dependent var	0.685911
S.E. of regression	0.456491	Akaike info criterion	1.293348
Sum squared resid	58.97280	Schwarz criterion	1.381932
Log likelihood	-180.5355	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.328839
F-statistic	61.58028	Durbin-Watson stat	1.888277
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		
BG Serial			
Correlation	3.753025		
Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0,153100		
BPG Heterosk. Test	7.376185		
Prob. Chi-Square(6)	0.287500		
Ramsey RESET	0.222000		

Prob. (F-statistic) 0.368000

Source: E-Views Version 12 Output Extract (2025)

The Table above presents the regression analysis that examined the moderating effect of emerging technology (ETEC) on the relationship between corporate fraud detection (CFDET) and the independent variables (FDMC, FITQ, FLSS). The R-squared tells us that 56.7% of the variation in corporate fraud detection is explained by the independent variables in the model, indicating a moderately strong fit. After accounting for the number of predictors, the adjusted R-squared shows that 55.7% of the variation in the dependent variable (CFDET) is still explained, confirming the model's robustness. When juxtaposed with the model one, we find that the interaction of emerging technologies has very little explanatory effect of 1.4% (55.7% minus 54.3%). This is equally buttressed by the insignificant t-statistics of most of the variables.

The p-value and F-statistic of 61.58 show that the model as a whole is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), demonstrating that the independent variables and its interactions collectively influence CFDET. The Durbin-Watson Statistic is 1.888. This value is close to 2, indicating no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test's insignificant p-value ($p = 0.153$) provides more evidence for this. The Table also reveals no evidence of heteroskedasticity as the p-value ($p = 0.288$) of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test is greater than 5%. In addition, there is no misspecification detected in the model as evidenced by the insignificant Ramsey RESET Test ($p = 0.638$).

On the individual t-statistics of the explanatory variables, FDMC with its interaction has insignificant positive relationship with CFDET. While FITQ has insignificant relationship, its interaction significantly contribute to CFDET in this model. Similarly, FLSS has a significant positive relationship; its interaction has an insignificant negative influence on CFDET.

Test of Hypotheses

To test the hypotheses generated earlier, this study relies on the main effect and the moderating effect. The decision rule is based on the significance of the p-value. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate is rejected if the p-value is greater than 5% or the alternate hypothesis is accepted while we fail to accept the null if the p-value is less than 5%.

Ho1: Fraud detection mechanisms do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

FDMC has a significant positive ($t = 5.187, p = 0.000$) influence on CFDET as evidenced by the low p-value. Therefore, we fail to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that fraud detection mechanisms significantly influence on corporate fraud detection.

Ho2: Fraud investigation techniques do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

FITQ does not significantly ($t = 1.367, p = 0.173$) influence CFDET as evidenced by the high p-value. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that fraud investigation techniques do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

Ho3: Fraud Litigation support services do not have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

FLSS has a significant positive ($t = 4.309$, $p = 0.000$) influence CFDET as evidenced by the small p-value. Therefore, we fail to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that fraud Litigation support services have significant influence on corporate fraud detection.

Ho4: Emerging technologies have no significant moderating influence on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection.

Based on the result in Table of the moderating effect, F-statistic of 115.321 and the related p-value show that the model as a whole is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), demonstrating that the independent variables and its interactions collectively influence CFDET. Therefore, we conclude based on the joint significance of the model that emerging technologies significantly moderate the influence of forensic accounting strategies on corporate fraud detection.

Discussion of findings

This section discusses the implications of the results from the analysis of data and the test of hypotheses as depicted in the regression outputs.

In the main effect, fraud detection mechanisms and fraud litigation support services findings showed a positive relationship and statistically significant influence on corporate fraud detection. The implementation of these results suggests that strong and effective fraud detection mechanisms; and fraud litigation support services in fraud detection and fraud management system in corporations. The result of fraud investigation techniques showed positive and non-significant influence on corporate fraud detection. This result implies that, an increase in fraud investigation techniques affects its relationship with corporate fraud detection by just 10%; but does not statistically influence corporate fraud detection. This result is not expected due to the perceived importance of fraud investigation techniques in fraud detection; apparently because there is variability of fraud investigation techniques since there are no generally accepted techniques in place for fraud detection, which suggest that if different investigation techniques are applied in any situation, the outcome of the investigation usually varies.

On the moderating aspect, the result showed that emerging technologies collective of (artificial intelligence, machine learning, and blockchain) is statistically significant in the overall model. This result implies that forensic accounting strategies and its interaction, collectively demonstrate significant moderating influence on the corporate fraud detection.

However, on the individual basis, while the interaction between FITQ and ETEC was statistically significant; the interactions between FDMC and FLSS with ETEC were statistically insignificant. These findings suggest that emerging technologies have varying moderating evidence on the relationship between these individual variables and corporate fraud detection. Furthermore, it is possible that each variable is not sufficiently predictive on its own to be statistically significant; which also means sample provides sufficient evidence to conclude that model is significant, but not enough to conclude that any individual variable is significant (Frost, 2024). Sometimes, lack of intention of the forensic accounting practitioners to accept, adopt, and use emerging technologies could have adverse effect on fraud detection, particularly if the users of these technologies do not have the technical-know-how to effectively and efficiently apply them.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection in Nigeria. Fraud seems to have defied various global initiatives made to control and manage increased fraudulent activities apparently due to advancement in modern technologies; complex environment for business operations; and the usage of traditional system for fraud prevention and detection. These traditional/conventional methods of fraud detection have been considered insufficient means to deal with fraud and fraudulent occurrences. This study is in response to the call for the need for more proactive measures to curtail the persistence threat to corporations' existence.

A valid and reliable structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study from primary sources in order to accomplish the research purpose. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to statistically analyse the data using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) (version 22), and E-View Statistical Analytic Tool (version 12). The findings of the study conclude with varies expectation from the hypotheses tested.

Fraud detection mechanisms and fraud litigation support services results showed positive association and significant influence on corporate fraud detection; fraud investigation techniques showed a positive relationship and insignificant influence on corporate fraud detection; and lastly, emerging technologies results showed statistically significant moderating influence on corporate fraud detection in the overall model. However, on the individual basis, while fraud investigation techniques showed significant moderating influence on corporate fraud detection; fraud detection mechanisms and fraud litigation support services, exhibited insignificant moderating influence on corporate fraud detection respectively.

Notwithstanding the shortcomings, this study contributes to knowledge as it has provided valuable insights into the moderating influence of emerging technologies on the relationship between forensic accounting strategies and corporate fraud detection in Nigeria; as well as complimented the perceived inadequate traditional-based system of combating corporate fraud and other fraudulent behaviours in Nigeria.

The study recommends among others, the need to always engage in proactive measures in the areas of forensic accounting and emerging technology that will inhibit the menace of fraud and fraud related misconducts in Nigerian business environment; amid the general perception that adoption and application of forensic accounting strategies and relevant emerging technologies are effective and efficient in combating and reducing fraudulent financial activities to low ebb in any economy.

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